

**ASPERGILLUS FUMIGATUS ZAMBURUG‘INI IKKILAMCHI
METABOLITLARINI AJRATISH VA BIOLOGIK FAOLLIGINI
O‘RGANISH**

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Annotation: Currently, under the specific climatic and ecological conditions of our republic, the cultivation of agricultural crops and increasing their productivity are among the most pressing issues in the sector. When searching for measures to enhance plant growth, development, and yield under the conditions of the republic, it is essential to take into account its unique ecological and natural factors. Such factors include soil salinization, contamination with various xenobiotics, as well as relatively high average temperatures during the long vegetation period. Under such conditions, thermotolerant and thermophilic fungi that are capable of developing at high temperatures and, at the same time, act as intermediaries in plant–microbe interactions by synthesizing physiologically active compounds, play an important role.

Keywords: Mycotoxins, antifungal activity, thermotolerant fungi, metabolite biosynthesis, fermentation process, extraction methods, structural analysis

Аннотация: В настоящее время в специфических климатических и экологических условиях нашей республики выращивание сельскохозяйственных культур и повышение их урожайности являются одними из актуальных проблем отрасли. При разработке мер по улучшению роста, развития и урожайности растений в условиях республики необходимо учитывать её специфические экологические и природные факторы. К таким факторам относятся засоление почв, загрязнение различными ксенобиотиками, а также относительно высокие средние температуры в течение длительного вегетационного периода. В этих условиях особую роль играют термотолерантные и термофильные грибы, способные развиваться при высоких температурах и одновременно выступающие посредниками во взаимодействии растений и микроорганизмов за счёт синтеза физиологически активных веществ.

Ключевые слова: Микотоксины, противогрибковая активность, термотолерантные грибы, биосинтез метаболитов, процесс ферментации, методы экстракции, структурный анализ

Annotatsiya: Hozirgi kunda Respublikamizning o‘ziga xos iqlim va ekologik sharoitlarida qishloq ho‘jalik ekinlarini yetishtirish, ularning hosildorligini oshirish tarmoqdagi dolzarb muammolardan hisoblanadi. Respublika sharoitlarida

o‘simliklarning o‘shishi, rivojlanishi va hosildorligini oshirish chora–tadbirlarini izlashda, avvalo uning o‘ziga hos bo‘lgan ekologik hamda tabiiy omillarni e‘tibordan soqit qilib bo‘lmaydi. Bunday omillarga tuproq sho‘rlanishi, uning turli ksenobiotiklar bilan zararlanganligi hamda uzun vegetatsion davr mobaynida o‘rtacha haroratning ancha yuqori bo‘lishi kiradi. Bunday vaqtlarda ayniqsa, yuqori haroratlarda rivojlana oladigan, shu bilan bir qatorda o‘simlik va mikroorganizmlar interaksiyasida oraliq vosita hisoblanuvchi – fiziologik faol moddalar sintezlovchi termotolerant va termofil zamburug‘lar muhim o‘rin tutadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Mikotoksinlar, antifungal faoliyat, termotolerant zamburug‘lar, metabolitlar biosintezi, fermentatsiya jarayoni, ekstraksiya usullari, strukturaviy tahlil

Kirish

O‘zbekiston Respublikasida sanoatning turli sohalari va qishloq ho‘jalik ekinlarining hosildorligini oshirishda termotolerant va termofil zamburug‘lar, ularning ikkilamchi metabolitlaridan keng foydalanishga alohida e‘tibor qaratilmoqda. Ta‘kidlash joizki, zamburug‘larning ayrim vakillari qator stress sharoitlarda, jumladan, qurg‘oqchilik, sho‘rlanish, turli kimyoviy birikmalar (neft va neft mahsulotlari, ksenobiotiklar) bilan zararlangan muhitlarga moslasha olishi muhim hisoblanadi. Bu borada, fiziologik faol moddalarning asosiy guruhini tashkil etuvchi fitogormonlar stress sharoitlarda o‘simliklarni o‘shishi va rivojlanishini ta‘minlaydi. Shu sababli, qishloq ho‘jaligi ekinlarini o‘shishi, rivojlanishi va noqulay sharoitlarga moslashishida fitogormonlar sintezlovchi mikroorganizmlardan foydalanish muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Rizosfera mikroorganizmlari o‘simliklarning o‘shishi va rivojlanishida muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ular o‘simliklarni oziq moddalar, garmonlar, vitaminlar va boshqa fiziologik faol birikmalarga bo‘lgan ehtiyojini ma‘lum darajada ta‘minlanishiga yordam beradi. Bundan tashqari ular o‘simliklarning yaxshi o‘sib rivojlanishiga, turli xildagi kasalliklarga chalinmasligiga va ularning hosildorligining ortishiga ijobiy ta‘sir ko‘rsatadi.

Mitselial zamburug‘lar rivojlanishi jarayonida auksin (AU), gibberellin (GK) va indol sirka kislotalarini (ISK) sintezlaydi. Ushbu biologik faol moddalar urug‘larning unishini, o‘simliklarning rivojlanishini tezlashtirish va hosildorligini oshirish maqsadida tayyorlanadigan biopreparatlarning asosiy komponenti bo‘lib hisoblanadi.

Ayniqsa, *Aspergillus* turkumiga mansub turlari aynan o‘simliklar urug‘ini unishiga, rivojlanishiga va hosildorligiga sezilarli stimullovchi ta‘sirga ega fitogarmonlarni sintezlash xususiyatiga ega bo‘lib, ushbu faol zamburug‘ shtammlari assosatsiyasi asosida ekologik toza biopreparat yaratish qishloq xo‘jaligi ekinlaridan yuqori va samarali hosil olish imkonini beradi.

Shuning uchun, fitogarmonlar sintezlovchi zamburug' shtammlarini tanlash, tanlab olingan shtammlar uchun optimal ozuqa muhitini yaratish (turli xil uglerod va azot manbalarining ta'siri hamda ko'p miqdorda ISK va GK hosil qilishi uchun suyuq ozuqa muhitida o'stirish sharoitlarini optimallashtirish va ularning ISK va GK hosil qilishini dinamikada o'rganish, qishloq xo'jaligi ekinlarining hosildorligiga stimullovchi ta'sir qiluvchi mikromitsetlar asosida ekologik toza biopreparatlar yaratish ilmiy-amaliy ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Antagonistik xususiyatga ega bo'lgan zamburug' *Aspergillus fumigatus* shtammining toza kulturalarini ajratishda quyidagi usuldan foydalanildi. Zamburug'larning toza kulturalarini ajratishda A.I. Netrusovning tuproq namunalarini qattiq ozuqa muhitiga to'g'ridan to'g'ri ekish usulidan foydalanildi. Tanlab olingan zamburug'larning shtammlari quyidagi ozuqa muhitida o'stirildi: Chapek ((g/l): saxaroza – 20.0, NaNO₃ – 3.0, KH₂PO₄ – 1.0, MgSO₄ – 0.5, KCl – 0.5, FeSO₄ – 0.01, suv – 1000 ml, agar – 20–30.), Mandels ((g/l): KH₂PO₄ – 1.0, (NH₄)₂HPO₄ – 2.3, MgSO₄ – 0.5, CaCl₂ – 0.3, mikroelementlar eritmasi – 1 ml), suslo-agar (7 ball), saburo ((g/l): glyukoza yoki maltoza – 40.0, pepton – 10.0, agar – 18.0, dis. suv – 1) ozuqa muhitlarida, 35-45°S haroratda o'rganildi. Qayta-qayta ekishlar asosida kulturalar tozalanib, ularning morfologik-kultural xususiyatlari, mitseliy rangi va tuzilishi, konidiya va konidiyalar tashuvchilari umumiy qabul qilingan usullar yordamida XSP-136B elektron mikroskopida mikroskopik tuzilishi tadqiq etildi. Ozuqa muhitlarining r n i 3 dan 7.0 gacha o'zgartirilib, 0,1 % li HCl yordamida nordonlashtirish orqali boshqarib borildi.

Aspergillus fumigatus shtammini 3, 7, 14, 20 kun davomida Chapek va Mandels ozuqa muhitida o'stirib, zamburug' shtammlarning ikkilamchi metabolitlarining tuzilishi va miqdoriy o'zgarishlari o'rganildi.

"Silufol" plastinkasida yupqa qatlamli xromatografiya (YUQX) o'tkazildi. YUQXda moddalar fosfornovolfram kislotasining 25% etanoli eritmasini purkash bilan sifat analiz orqali aniqlanildi va 5 minut davomida 100-110 °S haroratda qizdiriladi.

1–rasm. Aspergillus fumigatus shtammida gibberillin va gibberillin sintezlanishiga turli azot manbalarining ta’siri

Yuqoridagilardan kelib chiqib, bu shtamlarning biomassasini oshirish, ularda gibberillin va indolsirka kislota sintezini kuchaytirishda azot manbalaridan (NH₄)₂SO₄ va NaNO₃ tuzlaridan foydalanish tavsiya etiladi.

Keyingi tadqiqotlarda uglerod manbalarining gibberillin va indolsirka kislota sinteziga ta’siri o’rganildi. Uglerod manbasi sifatida sellyuloza, saxaroza (nazorat), glyukoza, laktoza, galaktoza, ramnoza, raffinoza, maltoza, fruktoza va mannitdan foydalanildi. Tajribalar davomida uglerod manbalarining ikkilamchi metabolitlar sinteziga sezilarli darajada ta’sir ko’rsatishi kuzatildi. Tajribalarda o’stirishning birinchi haftasida gibberillin sintezi faol bo’lgan bo’lsa, ikkinchi haftasida asosan indolsirka kislota sintezlanishi aniqlandi.

1-jadval

Geksanli fraksiyadan aniqlangan Aspergillus fumigatus zamburug’ining ikkilamchi metabolitlari:

No	Metabolit nomlari	Kimyoviy formula	Molekuly ar massa g/mol	Yutilish vaqti
1	(1R,4R,4aS,8aR)-4,7-Dimethyl-1-(prop-1-en-2-yl)-1,2,3,4,4a,5,6,8a-octahydronaphthalene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	204.3511	11,402
2	1H-Cycloprop[e]azulene, 1a, 2, 3, 4, 4a, 5, 6, 7b-octahydro-1, 1, 4, 7-tetramethyl	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	204.35	11,535
3	7-epi-trans-sesquisabinene hydrate	C ₁₅ H ₂₆	222.37	11,628
4	Tricyclo[5.2.2.0(1,6)]undecan-3-ol, 2-methylene-6,8,8-trimethyl-	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ O	220.35	12,273

5	Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl-	$C_{17}H_{36}$	240.5	12,448
6	(1R,7S,E)-7-Isopropyl-4,10-dimethylenecyclodec-5-enol	$C_{15}H_{24}O$	220.3505	12,696
7	Cedren-13-ol, 8-	$C_{15}H_{24}O$	220.3505	12,789
8	Longipinocarveol, trans-	$C_{15}H_{24}O$	220.35	13,004
9	2(1H)Naphthalenone, 3,5,6,7,8,8a-hexahydro-4,8a-dimethyl-6-(1-methylet	$C_{15}H_{22}O$	218.3346	13,276
10	1H-Cyclopenta[a]pentalen-7-ol, decahydro-3,3,4,7a-tetramethyl-, 4-methy	$C_{17}H_{28}O_2$	264.4	13,405
11	Dihydroxanthin	$C_{17}H_{24}O_5$	308.4	13,713
12	2-[4-methyl-6-(2,6,6-trimethylcyclohex-1-enyl)hexa-1,3,5-trienyl]cyclohex-1	$C_{23}H_{32}O$	324.5	14,423
13	2-Hydroxy-4,4,8-trimethyltricyclo[6.3.1.0(1,5)]dodecan-9-one	$C_{15}H_{24}O_2$	236.35	14,692
14	l-(+)-Ascorbic acid 2,6-dihexadecanoate	$C_{38}H_{68}O_8$	652.9	15,100
15	Hexadecanoic acid, ethyl este	$C_{17}H_{34}O_2$	270.4507	15,287
16	Bicyclo[9.3.1]pentadeca-3,7-dien-12-ol, 4,8,12,15,15-pentamethyl-, [1R-(1	$C_{20}H_{34}O$	290.4834	15,491
17	1-Heptatriacotanol	$C_{37}H_{76}O$	537.0	15,752
18	17-Pentatriacontene	$C_{35}H_{70}$	490.9	15,975
19	cis-13-Octadecenoic acid	$C_{18}H_{34}O_2$	282.5	16,240
20	Octadecanoic acid	$C_{18}H_{36}O_2$	284.5	16,361
21	(E)-9-Octadecenoic acid ethyl ester	$C_{20}H_{38}O_2$	310.5	16,401
22	Heptadecanoic acid, 15-methyl-, ethyl ester	$C_{19}H_{38}O_2$	298.5038	16,541
23	4,8,13-Cyclotetradecatriene-1,3-diol, 1,5,9-trimethyl-12-(1-methylethyl)-	$C_{20}H_{34}O_2$	306.5	17,254
24	9-(2',2'-Dimethylpropanoilhydrazono)-3,6-dichloro-2,7-bis-[2-(diethylamino)	$C_{30}H_{42}Cl_2N_4O_3$	577.6	18,558
25	Octadecane, 3-ethyl-5-(2-ethylbutyl)-	$C_{26}H_{54}$	366.7	19,776

Tuzilishi aniqlangan metabolitlarning biologik xususiyatlari o‘rganilganda asosiy qismi efirsimon moddalar va terpinoid guruhlariga xos moddalar bo‘lib, antimikrob, antioksidant va yallig‘lanishga qarshi ta’sirga ega ekanligi aniqlandi. Octadecanoic acid guruhiga kiruvchi birikmalar (19,20,21,25) yarali yallig‘lanishga qarshi, hipokolesterolemik, saratonni oldini olish, gepatoprotetive, nematidid, antiekzemik, 5-alfa reduktaza ingibitori ekanligi bir adabiyotlarda keltirilgan. Geksanli fraksiyada olingan 25 ta metabolitlardan ko‘p qismi past

molekulyar yogʻ kislotali moddalar ekanligi aniqlandi. Yogʻ kislotali metabolitlar yoki to'yinmagan yogʻ kislotalar antifungal samaradorligi zanjir uzunligining oshib borishi bilan ortadi. Aniqlangan metabolitlarning ayrimlari tibbiyot va kosmetika sohasiga oid istiqbolli moddalar sifatida qo'llaniladi.

Xromatografik kolonkadagi ekstraktlarni taqsimlashlarga ajratish geksandan olingan elyuent sifatida xloroformda davom ettirildi. Xloroformli fraksiyalarda moddalar ajralishiga qarab YuQX qo'yib borildi. YuQX uchun xloroform - metanol 19:1 sistemadan foydalanildi. Xromatografik plastinkada yagona pik bergan fraksiya yig'ib borildi va Rf nuqtalari aniqlandi. Rf nuktasi 0,77 ga tengligi aniqlandi (3-rasm). Xloroformlidagi ikkilamchi metabolitlar GSH da aniqlandi (3-rasm).

2-rasm. Xloroformli fraksiyaning yupqa qatlamli va gaz suyuqlik xromatografiyasi

Tajriba davomida GSX xromatografiyasida aniqlangan uchuvchan metabolitlar MS ma'lumolar bazasida idenfikatsiya qilindi. (2-jadval)

2-jadval

Aspergillus fumigatus zamburugʻining Xloroformli fraksiyada aniqlangan ikkilamchi metabolitlari

No	Metabolit nomlari	Kimyoviy formula	Molekulyar modda g/mol	Yutilish vaqti
1	Undecylenic acid	$C_{11}H_{20}O_2$	184.27	11,255
2	9-Oxononanoic acid	$C_9H_{16}O_3$	172.22	11,639
3	Isopropyl palmitate	$C_{19}H_{38}O_2$	298.511	11,700
4	Cyclopentadecanone, 2-hydroxy-	$C_{15}H_{28}O_2$	240.3816	12,821
5	9-Octadecynoic acid, methyl ester	$C_{19}H_{34}O_2$	294.4721	12,957
6	9,12-Octadecadienoyl chloride, (Z,Z)-	$C_{18}H_{31}ClO$	298.9	13,588
7	Tetradecanoic acid	$C_{14}H_{28}O_2$	228.37	13,685
8	Geranyl isovalerate	$C_{15}H_{26}O_2$	238.37	13,807
9	Pentadecanoic acid	$C_{15}H_{30}O_2$	242.40	14,394
10	n-Hexadecanoic acid	$C_{16}H_{32}O_2$	256.4241	15,304
11	Heptadecanoic acid	$C_{17}H_{34}O_2$	270.5	15,777

12	Oleic Acid	$C_{18}H_{34}O_2$	282.5	16,422
13	Octadecanoic acid	$C_{18}H_{36}O_2$	284.5	16,501
14	1-Naphthalenepropanol, a-ethenyldecahydro-2-hydroxy-a,2,5,5,8a-pentam	$C_{20}H_{36}O_2$	308.5	16,806
15	1,3,6,10-Cyclotetradecatetraene, 3,7,11-trimethyl-14-(1-methylethyl)	$C_{20}H_{32}$	272.5	17,046
16	7,10,13-Eicosatrienoic acid, methyl ester	$C_{21}H_{36}O_2$	320.5	17,182
17	Oxiraneoctanoic acid, 3-octyl-, cis-	$C_{19}H_{36}O_3$	312.5	17,741
18	Diisooctyl phthalate	$C_{24}H_{38}O_4$	390.6	18,594

GSX-MS ma'lumotlar bazasida aniqlangan uchuvchan metabolitlar ichida, Undecylenic acid, Pentadecanoic acid metaboliti *Myrothecium verrucaria*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* nisbatan, Heptadecanoic acid metaboliti *Botrytis cinerea*, *Cladosporium cucumerinum*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Phytophthora infestans*, *Pythium aphanidermatum*, *Sphaerotheca fuliginea* ga nisbatan, Oleic Acid uchuvchan metaboliti *Crinipellis perniosa*, *Pythium ultimum* ga nisbatan yuqori antimikroblik xususiyatlariga ega ekanligi adabiyot manbalarida ma'lum. Tetradecanoic acid, 9-Octadecynoic acid, methyl ester, 9,12-Octadecadienoyl chloride, (Z,Z)-, Octadecanoic acid metabolitlari esa yarali yallig'lanishga qarshi, hipokolesterolemik, saratonni oldini olish, gepatoprotektiv, nematitsid, antiyekzemik, 5-alfa reduktaza ingibatori hisoblanadi.

Xulosa

Aspergillus fumigatus zamburug'ining asosiy metabolitlari fenollar va terpenoidlar guruhiga mansub moddalar ekanligi va ushbu metabolitlar antimikrob, yallig'lanishlarga qarshi vosita, nematitsit va antiyekzemik yallig'lanishga qarshi ikkilamchi metabolitlar ekanligi aniqlandi. Terpenoidlar yer yuzidagi eng ko'p tarqalgan tabiiy birikmalar bo'lib, turli xil uchuvchan va uchuvchan bo'lmagan ikkilamchi metabolitlarni o'z ichiga oladi. Ularning ko'pchiligi zamburug'lar tomonidan sintez qilinadi.

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